

Works Performed Under MGNREGA: Perception across Gender and Socio-Economic Status at Bazar Community, Lawngtlai, Mizoram

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Abstract- The MGNREGA is recognized as a major project for reducing and alleviating rural poverty. The emergence of jobs brought about changes in the rural society. The scheme's nature and purpose were meant to benefit the rural poor. Several essential long-term goals of MGNREGA include providing social protection to the poor in rural areas. The scheme has led to the creation of assets in the villages. The findings show that weed removal and the use of machinery were practiced in Lawngtlai. However, there are no significant differences in the perception of works performed under MGNREGA with gender and socio-economic status. The difference in the perception of non-permissible work performed across gender and socioeconomic status is not significant.

Index Terms- MGNREGA, Gender, Socio economic, works performed.

I. INTRODUCTION

The MGNREGA is recognized as a major project for reducing and alleviating rural poverty. The emergence of jobs brought about changes in the rural society. The scheme's nature and purpose were meant to benefit the rural poor. The scheme's provisions include but are not limited to, social protection, the formation of long-term assets, drought mitigation measures, flood management, and the welfare of disadvantaged groups in society. Several essential long-term goals of MGNREGA include providing social protection to the poor in rural areas through increase in employment opportunities, creating durable assets in rural areas; providing drought-proofing and flood management in rural India, and empowering socially disadvantaged groups.

The accomplishment of the aims would verify the effectiveness of its execution. The MGNREGS has given rise to the greatest employment program in the world. Its bottom-up, people-centered, demand-driven, self-selecting, right-based design is different and unparalleled. MGNREGA is not just a welfare initiative, it is also a development endeavor that may push the Indian economy to a new road of advancement. The aims of MGNREGA may be described in three words: - Protective, Preventive, and Promotive (Arya et al. 2017).

II. Literature review

Several studies have investigated the execution of MGNREGA in different regions of India. Natesan (2021) and Dey (2014) both note the need for changes in wage determination and productivity assessment, with Natesan especially concentrating on Tamil Nadu and Dey on Rajasthan. Seth (2015) presents a mixed review of the system, citing its beneficial influence on employment and self-reliance in certain places, including the prevalence of unscrupulous activities and prejudice in labor allocation. Gupta (2023) gives a geographical study of MGNREGA implementation in Uttarakhand, stressing the effect of land use and terrain on the distribution of activities. These studies collectively underline the necessity for continuing review and improvement in the implementation of MGNREGA. Dhananjaya (2011) stressed the necessity for MGNREGA to focus on boosting agricultural output to develop associated livelihoods. Mishra (2018) underlined the need to establish productive assets connected to agriculture and associated industries, and the need for sustainable growth in the agriculture sector.

III. Statement of the problem

In India, to tackle the problem of poverty, the Government of India developed numerous policies and programs including the Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act (MGNREGA). One of the key aims of the project is to give job opportunities and contribute significantly towards the general development of the people. The operational rules clearly outline the acceptable and the non-permissible work. This study seeks to assess the works undertaken in the setting of Bazar Community, Lawngtlai.

IV. Methodology

The study is descriptive in its design and it is based on Primary Data. The data was collected using quantitative method with the help of structured interview schedule. Disproportionate stratified random sampling was employed in which the community was divided into different strata based on the existing two YLA Sections. 30 households were selected from both the YLA Sections using systematic random sampling. The unit of the study is the household and all the MGNREGS beneficiary's households within Bazar Community, Lawngtlai constitute the population. The sample size is 60 households. The population of the study is households having job card under MGNREGA in Bazar Community, Lawngtlai.

V. Structural basis of the respondents

The Demographic characteristics of the respondents were divided into various sections such as Gender, Educational qualification, Occupation, Annual income, socioeconomic category, size of family, type of family, and form of family. The gender distribution of respondents shows that female constitute 75% and male constitute 25% with a mean age of 44. In terms of educational qualification, the respondents in the present study consist of primary school (20%), high school (50%), higher secondary school (20%), and postgraduate (10%). In terms of occupation, 20% of the family are Government employees, Business (30%), and agriculture and livestock farmers 50%. Among the respondents, 20% and 80% belong to the poor and non-poor Socio-Economic Category respectively. The respondents belong to the nuclear family (90%) and joint family (10%). 80% of the respondents belong to a family size of 1-5 members with a mean score of 4.56. The majority of the respondents belong to stable families (90%).

Table No. 1. Profile of the respondents

SI. No.	Particulars		Frequency	%
1	Gender	Male	15	25
		Female	45	75
2	Educational Qualification	Middle	12	20
		High School	30	50
		Higher Secondary	12	20
		Under Graduate	0	0
		Post Graduate	6	10
4	Occupation	Govt. Employee	12	20
		Business	18	30
		Agriculture and Livestock Farmers	30	50
5	Socio Economic Category	Poor	12	20
		Non- Poor	48	80
6	Type of Family	Nuclear	54	90
		Joint	6	10
7	Form of Family	Stable	54	90
		Dysfunctional	6	10

Source: Computed

VI. Types of work

The types of work performed in the community as per the knowledge of the respondents are retaining walls, terracing, side drains, linkage road, construction road, construction of pit latrine, construction of link road, and road tree plantation. 75% of the respondents opted sometimes in work related to the construction and maintenance of retaining. 85% of the respondents opted sometimes in the construction of terracing, and more than half of the respondents (95%) claim that the construction of the side drain is done. All the respondents agree that the link road is constructed. The respondents opted sometimes for the construction of latrines (65) and tree plantation (85).

Table No. 2. Types of work under MGNREGA

SI.No.	Particulars	Always	Sometimes	Never
1	Retaining wall	6 (10)	45(75)	9(15)
2	Terracing	9(15)	51(85)	0(0)
3	Side Drain	3(5)	57(95)	0(0)
4	Link Road	3(5)	57(95)	0(0)
6	Construction of Latrine	3(5)	39(65)	18(30)
8	Tree Plantation	3(5)	51(85)	6(10)

Source: computed Figures in parentheses are percentage

To analyze the difference between male and female in terms of perception towards works conducted under MGNREGA, Mann Whitney U Test was employed. The test found revealed insignificant differences in the perception of male and female, $U=27.5$, $z=0.921$, $p=0.357$.

To examine the difference between poor and non-poor in terms of perception towards activities completed under MGNREGS, Mann Whitney U Test was employed. The test he test revealed insignificant differences in the perception of poverty and non-poor, $U=26.500$, $z=.548$, $p=.548$.

Table No. 3. Perception on MGNREGS works undertaken based on Socio Economic Category and gender

	Socio Economic Category	Gender
Mann-Whitney U	26.500	27.5
Wilcoxon W	36.500	147.5
Z	.548	0.921
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	.584	0.357

Source: computed

VII. Non-Permissible work:

The findings show that harvesting, watering, turning the soil, digging of private wells, and floriculture have never been done in the community. 95% of the respondents said that land preparation is never performed under MGNREGS. Plowing is claimed to be performed sometimes (40%) while 60% stated that it was not done. Weed Removal is done but not regularly (90%). Agriculture operations for food grain crops, vegetables, floriculture, etc. got a score of 60% and 40% in the category of sometimes and never. However, the use of machinery is realized as 80% of the respondents claimed that it is done sometimes.

Table No. 4. Non-Permissible work

Sl.No.	Particulars	Always	Sometimes	Never
1	Land Preparation	0(0)	3(5)	57(95)
2	Harvesting	0(0)	0(0)	60(100)
3	Plowing	0(0)	24(40)	36(60)
4	Watering	0(0)	0(0)	60(100)
5	Turning the Soil	0(0)	0(0)	60(100)
6	Weed Removal	0(0)	54(90)	6(10)
7	Floriculture	0(0)	0(0)	60(100)
8	Agriculture operation for food grain crops, vegetables, floriculture etc.	0(0)	36(60)	24(40)
9	Digging of private well	0(0)	0(0)	60(100)
10	Use Of Machinery	0(0)	48(80)	12(20)

Source: Computed Figures in parentheses are percentage

To analyze the difference between male and female in terms of perception towards non permissible work undertaken under MGNREGS, Mann Whitney U Test was used. The test revealed insignificant differences in the perception of male and female, $U=34$, $z=0.318$, $p=0.751$.

To examine the difference between poor and non-poor in terms of perception towards non permissible work undertaken under MGNREGS, Mann Whitney U Test was used. The test revealed insignificant differences in the perception of poor and non-poor, $U=26.500$, $z=.541$, $p=.589$.

Table No. 5. Perception on Non permissible work performed based on socio Economic Category and gender

	Gender	Socio Economic Category
Mann-Whitney U	34	26.500
Wilcoxon W	154	36.500
Z	0.318	.541
Asymp. Sig. (2-tailed)	0.751	.589

Source: Computed

VIII. Conclusion

The majority of the rural population mainly depends on agriculture and unskilled labor which makes them prone to become a victim of poverty. In response to this, the Government of India implemented the MGNREGA. The implementation of MGNREGA in Mizoram began in the 2006-07 Financial Year in which Lawngtlai and Siah Districts are under Phase 1. The scheme has led to the creation of assets in the villages. The findings show that weed removal and the use of machinery were practiced in Lawngtlai. However, there are no significant differences in the perception of works performed under MGNREGA with gender and socio-economic status. The difference in the perception of non-permissible work performed across gender and socioeconomic status is not significant.

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